

PROCESSING AND PROPERTIES OF MULTISCALE CARBON NANOFIBRE FILLED CARBON/EPOXY COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY

Multiscale carbon nanofibre (CNF) filled carbon/epoxy composites have been manufactured by hand lay-up and cured by vacuum bagging and hot pressing. The effect of the incorporation of different CNFs contents in thermal and mechanical properties has been studied.

Keywords: Nanocomposites, Multiscale composites, Carbon fibre, Carbon nanofibres, Epoxy

INTRODUCTION

Epoxy is by far the most widely used polymer matrix for carbon fibres. These composites are especially high in their specific strength and specific toughness in comparison with other fibre reinforced plastic (FRP). The main problem is that with out-of-plane loads or impacts these composites are vulnerable to interlaminar delamination. The incorporation of CNFs improves the interlaminar properties [1]. The increases in these mechanical properties are moderate due to the poor dispersion and highly entangled nanoreinforcements with very limited volume fraction and/or low interfacial strength [2]. In present work, the microstructure and thermo-mechanical and flexural properties of multiscale composites with different contents of CNFs have been studied.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

The epoxy matrix used in this study consists on a polymer based Bisphenol A resin, diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A (DGEBA), with 178 g/epoxy equivalent, manufactured by *Ciba* (commercial name of Araldite F) and an aromatic amine hardener (4,4-methylenedianiline, DDM) supplied by Sigma Aldrich. Vapour grown CNFs provided by *Antolin Company* were used as nanoreinforcements. Their diameters were in the range from 20 to 47 nm and its average length was 35 μm . The morphology of nanoreinforcements was analyzed in previous researchers [3]. The CNFs were fundamentally constituted by two types of nanofibres, “cup-staked”, with a disposition in which the graphite planes were oriented with a body cone shape, and “platelet-like” nanofibres, in which the CNFs tended to get entangled with helical dispositions.

Two dimensional plain weave IM7 carbon fibre manufactured by *Hexcel* was used in this study. The vacuum bagging materials used for the manufacturing of multiscale composites were: bagging film NBF-540-LFT, release film, liquid antiadherent demoulding agent Marbocote 445, polyester film and vacuum bag sealant tapes TV-200-Y. All materials were supplied by INP 96.

Manufacturing of multiscale composites

Multiscale composites panels were manufactured using plain weave carbon fibre and CNF/epoxy mixtures with different contents (0.5 and 1 wt.%) of CNFs as nanoreinforcement.

The CNFs were dispersed in the epoxy matrix using the method optimized in previous studies [4,5]. CNFs were dispersed in chloroform solvent by magnetic stirring at 40 °C for 30 minutes. DGBEA was mixed with the nanofibres suspensions and sonicated using a 50–60 Hz for 45 min at 40 °C. The chloroform was evaporated with continuous stirring in a vacuum oven at 90 °C for 24 h. And finally, a stoichiometric amount of DDM was added into the DGBEA/CNF mixture with stirring at 130 °C during 3 minutes. These mixtures DGBEA/CNF were then used as matrix to manufacture multiscale composites.

The multiscale composites were fabricated by the following procedure. First, the tool surface was cleaned with acetone and an antiadherent demoulding agent was added to the surface to allow the easy release of the panel. Then, four layers of weave carbon fibre, measuring approximately 10 cm by 15 cm, were laid on the tool. The CNF/epoxy mixtures were impregnated using a brush by hand lay-up process in each woven carbon fibre. The curing of the CF/CNF/epoxy panels has been made following two types of processes: vacuum bagging and hot pressing.

For the cured by vacuum bagging, a layer of vacuum bag sealant tape is placed around the perimeter of the tool. The release film was laid above panels and to obtain a homogeneous thickness a steel plate was placed on the top of the panels. The complete assembly was covered with a polyester fabric, to distribute the vacuum through all material, and with a heat resistant vacuum bag. Finally, it was placed in the oven for 15 minutes at 150 °C. After this pre-cured time, full vacuum was applied and the panels were cured in vacuum during 3 hours at 150 °C. CF/CNF/epoxy panels were post-cured at 180 °C for 1 hour in a stove. In the case of cured by hot pressing, CF/CNF/epoxy panels were covered with a release film and a steel plate. Panels were pre-cured in the hot plate, nearing the plates of the press without applying load, at 150 °C during 15 minutes. Later, panels were cured in hot plate press at 150 °C for 3 hours applying 200 kN. In parallel, neat CF/epoxy panels were fabricated by using the same methods to compare with the nanoreinforced panels.

Characterisation and mechanical testing

The CF/epoxy and CF/CNF/Epoxy microstructure was studied by optical microscopy (OM), environmental scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and field emission gun scanning electron microscopy (FEGSEM).

A Mettler Toledo balance, with ± 0.01 mg, equipped with a density determination kit by means the buoyancy technique, was used to evaluate the modification of density in cured multiscale materials by the incorporation of different contents of nanofibres. Five

measurements were done for each specimen and three specimens were measured for each kind of sample studied, determining the average value.

The coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) was measured using a Thermal Mechanical Analyser (TMA Q400) by TA Instruments. The measurement was carried out for a temperature range from 25 °C to 200 °C and a heating rate of 10 °C/min.

A DMTA Q800 equipped from TA Instrument was used to determine the thermal and mechanical properties of the CF/epoxy and CF/CNF/epoxy composites. Experiments were carried out operating in single cantilever mode with an oscillation frequency of 1.0 Hz. Data were collected from room temperature to 250 °C at a scanning rate of 2 °C/min. DMTA samples measuring 1.5 x 12 x 35 mm³ were cut from panels of CF/epoxy and CF/CNF/epoxy composites.

For evaluating the flexural properties, specimens were tested under a three-flexural loading based on the standard ASTM D790-02. Flexural tests were carried out on an MTS servo-hydraulic test machine equipped with a 30 kN load cell. The typical specimen dimensions were 1.5 x 12 x 60 mm³. The span length, depended on specimen dimension, was around 25 mm. The fracture surfaces have been examined by SEM.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Microstructural characterization

The SEM examination allowed the evaluation of the general microstructure and porosity of multiscale composites. Figure 1 shows an optical micrograph of CF/epoxy composite (a) and SEM micrograph of CF/CNF/epoxy composite with 0.5 wt.% of CNFs (b). As it can be seen in these micrographs the porosity was very low and wettability of the carbon fibres by the epoxy matrix was adequate. On the other hand, the use of high resolution techniques, as field gun electron microscopy, permitted the evaluation of the nanofibres dispersion in the epoxy matrix located between the woven carbon fibre layers.

Figure 1. a) OM and b) SEM images of CF/epoxy and CF/0.5%CNF/epoxy composites.

Figure 2a shows the microstructure of the CF/CNF/epoxy composites cured by vacuum bagging. It was possible to detect the nanofibres in zones of the matrix with dark contrast. Because of their electrical conductivity, the epoxy matrix was not changed with the presence of nanoreinforcements. As shown in Figure 2a, the distribution of the nanofibres was not totally homogeneous and there were some agglomerates. Nevertheless, the quantity of these aggregates was small and the distribution of the nanofibres was homogeneous. When 1 wt.% of CNFs was added into the matrix, the dispersion degree was even worse (Figure 2b). The presence of these agglomerates indicated that there were areas free of nanofibres in the matrix. A detail of these agglomerates is shown in Figure 2c, in which is possible to identified the longer CNFs. Therefore, the CNFs dispersion in chloroform was not effective for percentages above 0.5 wt.%, as has been justified in other studies [4,5].

The analysis at high magnifications of the matrix between woven carbon fibres gave additional information about the dispersion grade and allowed the study of the interface nanofibre/epoxy. For this purpose and to reduce charging effects in the microscope, the surfaces were coated with a thin sputtered layer of Au/Pd. Figure 2d is a representative images of the integration of CNFs in the epoxy matrix. The zones where the nanofibres were well dispersed, there was a good continuity between epoxy and nanofibres. However in agglomerate zones, it was possible to detect some voids between the CNFs and the matrix indicating the lack of wettability.

Figure 2. FEGSEM images of CF/0.5%CNF/epoxy (a) and CF/1%CNF/epoxy composites (b, c and d).

Density

Table 1 collects the density of different materials manufactured by the two processing methods. The behaviour of the density was the same in both cases: the density increased at 0.5 % of CNFs and decreased at higher contents. When the nanoreinforcement was introduced homogeneously in the matrix, the CNFs could occupy the free volume of the epoxy network increasing the density of the composite [5]. However, when CNFs tended to agglomerate, the formation of defects associated with the voids inside the CNFs bundles caused a decreasing of density. Furthermore, the density values reached through the hot pressing method were higher. In this case, the pressure exerted over the resin impregnating weaves produced a higher compaction regards to the pressure applied by vacuum bagging.

Table 1. Density of multiscale composites with different CNFs contents.

	Curing	% in weight CNF		
		0	0.5	1
ρ (g/cm ³)	Vacuum bagging	1,25	1,37	1,31
	Hot pressing	1,29	1,42	1,32

Thermal and Thermomechanical properties

The changes in the thickness of the samples in function of the temperature have been registered through thermomechanical analysis. It possible to distinguish two zones in the curves, before (50-150 °C) and after (180-300 °C) the glass transition temperature. The thermal dilation coefficients can be obtained from the both slopes of the curve. The coefficients measured before and after Tg of multiscale composites with different CNFs contents are showed in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Effect of CNF content on CTE, below and above of Tg, of CF/epoxy and CF/CNF/epoxy composites cured by a) vacuum bagging and b) hot pressing.

The tendency of the measurements realized was the same at lower and higher temperatures than T_g and for both manufacturing methods. The CTE decreased with the incorporation of 0.5 % CNF and at higher percentage the value was constant or lightly increased. The tendency of the CTE can be explained from the distribution of the nanoreinforcements in the matrix. When the CNFs were better dispersed in the matrix, occupying the free volume of the epoxy network, contributed to the CTE drop. Again, the higher compaction reached in the hot pressing method allowed lower values of CTE than those from vacuum bagging method.

DMTA tests were carried out to evaluate mechanical properties and T_g from Tan Delta curve of different multiscale composites with different CNFs contents. Figure 4 and 5 show the variation of storage modulus (E') and Tan Delta with the temperature, respectively. The results obtained from the curve are resumed in Table 2.

Figure 4. Storage modulus vs. temperature curves of CF/epoxy and CF/CNF/epoxy composites cured by a) vacuum bagging and b) hot pressing.

Figure 5. Tan Delta vs. temperature curves of CF/epoxy and CF/CNF/epoxy composites cured by a) vacuum bagging and b) hot pressing.

Table 2. Effect of CNF content on storage modulus and Tg of CF/epoxy CF/CNF/epoxy composites processed by different curing methods.

Cured	% in weight CNF	E' _G (MPa) at 30 °C	E' _R (MPa) at 200 °C	Tg (°C)
Vacuum bagging	0	1479	2270	164.8
	0.5	20890	2978	163.9
	1	20054	2510	160.8
Hot pressing	0	16867	2741	168
	0.5	19794	2837	157.6
	1	18363	2637	161.5

For both manufacturing methods, an increase in the mechanical properties was detected with the incorporation of 0.5 % of nanoreinforcements and a slight decrease at 1 %. A high storage modulus was associated with the good dispersion of the nanoreinforcement in the matrix. Although some agglomerates were detected by electron microscopy, the interfacial bonding allowed the transmission of the load from the matrix to the nanoreinforcements, which improved the mechanical properties. The decrease at 1 % took place when there was lack of wettability between the CNFs and the matrix inside the agglomerates. Furthermore, in general, the storage modulus of multiscale composites was higher than of those non nanoreinforced in the rubbery region. This behaviour could be due to the reduced mobility of the epoxy matrix around the nanoreinforcements, which produced an increase of the thermal stability.

The maximum of Tan Delta vs. temperature curve was used to identify the glass transition temperature. As can be observed in Figure 4, the incorporation of CNFs into the matrix reduced the Tg. Several authors have associated this behaviour to the selective absorption of a matrix constituent by the CNFs [6], that led to non-stoichiometric balance, which produced the drop of the glass transition temperature. When CNFs were agglomerated at higher contents, it was difficult that took place the selective absorption process and the Tg was recovered.

Flexural properties

Flexural stress-strain curves of multiscale composites are shown in Figure 6. The curves show a first linear deformation and the posterior irregularities in the curves were attributed to the woven carbon fibres breakage during loading. Flexural results are collected in the Table 3.

The incorporation of CNFs in the epoxy matrix improved both the modulus and the strength regards to the neat system. The flexural properties increased for the 0.5 wt.% content, followed by a slight drop for the 1 wt.%. As have been explained in the thermomechanical properties section, the enhancement in the modulus may be due to the more homogeneous dispersion of the CNFs in the composite, that allowed a good transfer of load from the matrix to the CNFs. At higher concentrations of CNFs, the nanoreinforcement tended to agglomerate and this transference was not possible, dropping the properties.

The variations in strength were more significant than in modulus. Some authors hardly detected improvements in modulus because it was dominated by the carbon fibres present in the laminate. However, the presence of CNFs increased the crack propagation resistance by the bridging effect, which improved the strength [7].

Figure 6 shows the optical and the SEM image of failed multiscale composite. After the flexural test, the samples were not completely broken (Figure 7a) and it was manually made. Fibre breakage and pull-out were observed in both neat and multiscale composites (Figure 7b). The study of fracture surface SEM images allowed understanding the effect of CNFs addition in the multiscale composites failure mode. It is common to both systems (neat and nanoreinforced) the presence of handkle patterns, typical of a brittle epoxy in which matrix fracture produced a closely spaced array of cusp-shaped featured aligned normal to the fibres (Figure 7c).

Figure 6. Flexural stress-strain curves of CF/epoxy and CF/CNF/epoxy composites cured by a) vacuum bagging and b) hot pressing.

Table 3. Flexural properties of CF/epoxy CF/CNF/epoxy composites processed by different curing methods.

Properties	Curing	% in weight CNF		
		0	0.5	1
Modulus (GPa)	Vacuum bagging	33.2	46.2	39.2
	Hot pressing	32.9	46.5	30
Strenght (MPa)	Vacuum bagging	739	785.5	635.2
	Hot pressing	508.4	795.1	500.5

It is easiest to identified, in nanoreinforced composites, zones were CNFs tended to agglomerate in the layers of resin between woven carbon fibres. While neat epoxy

showed smooth fracture surface with river lines (Figure 8a); some zones where CNFs were located in nanoreinforced composites, presented rough surface associated to plastic deformation (Figure 8b). The presence of CNFs modified the fracture mode favouring the energy absorption during the test.

Figure 7. Optical and SEM images of failed CF/0.5%CNF/epoxy.

Figure 8. SEM images of the fracture surface under flexural tests of a) CF/epoxy and b) CF/0.5%CNF/epoxy.

CONCLUSIONS

The CNF dispersion grade in the epoxy matrix affected to the properties of the multiscale composites. The dispersion of CNFs, using the sonication method, was homogeneous up to 0.5 wt.% and at higher contents the presence of CNF agglomerates was significant.

At percentages up to 0.5 wt.%, the density increased and the coefficient of thermal expansion decreased regards to the neat matrix, due to the incorporation of the nanoreinforcement into the free volume of the epoxy network. The storage modulus and flexural properties increased because they were associated with the homogeneous dispersed CNFs and the adherence between the nanoreinforcement and the matrix, allowing the load transference. The Tg decrease due to the selective absorption of DDM by the nanoreinforcement that produced a non-stoichiometric curing reaction.

At higher percentages, the tendency of forming agglomerates caused low densities and high CTEs. The bundled nanoreinforcements do not contribute to the mechanical properties and cannot develop the selective absorption, increasing the Tg.

Regarding to the manufacturing procedure, in the hot pressing cure the higher compaction reached gave rise to better properties than those produced by vacuum bagging cure.

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